

Study of the Role and Importance of Futuristic & Fast Transportation Technology in Shaping the Bright Future of India

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Abstract: In the emerging world of technology, the transportation system is also progressing towards great level of achievements, one of such achievement is the new, updated and fastest transportation system named *Virgin Hyperloop One*, such technology is known for its very high-speed transportation technology. We can easily analyse its capability by knowing the fact that, It is capable of achieving the speed which is 4 times the speed of bullet train and double the speed of Boeing 747 plane. Such a modern system of transportation will start initialling to take its original structure in the year 2021. This modern technological-driven innovative system will help the people 'to stay anywhere', 'to work from anywhere', and 'to go to anywhere' from their native place with very much ease in the upcoming future. For such reason, the company set a goal to gets into a contract with Bangalore airport as well as the Punjab transportation department for actualization the scheme in India. Hyperloop is a brand-new grounded transport technology in development and implementation, which encourages various new corporation to come into existence, some of which are the already established techno-giants, it would see passengers move at over 1200 kilometres each hour in a very fast floating pod. Hyperloop will be cheaper and faster than train or automobile travel, and will produce almost no any polluting substances in the environment. Hyperloop would possibly therefore be accustomed take the pressure off gridlocked roads, making travel between cities easier, and probably unlocking major economic benefits for India. We can easily analyse the captive abilities of this new transportation system with the fact that it can complete the 3 hours of journey in just 35 minutes of time. And it's not any miracle, it's actually a reality. *Virgin Hyperloop One* is capable of transporting more than 200 million passengers every year, when it will start functioning in India. Such innovative and technology-driven advanced transportation system will bring various type of opportunities for the country India in the upcoming future, as such project will bring a very large amount of infrastructure-based investments from several corporates, that will directly or indirectly generate

the employment opportunities for over 1.8 million people and it will also generate a huge amount of economic profit for India, which can be estimated over US \$35 Billion.

Keywords: Hyperloop, Transport, Technology, High-Speed, Opportunities, Economic, Profit.

Article History

Received: 12/02/2021; Accepted: 06/03/2021

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Introduction

Transportation is a part of our everyday life. It is mixed with our daily routine very deeply, that no one can even expect of living their life without transportation. They are the various medium through which a person can transport from one place to another. Such as road transportation with the help of a car, bike, truck, buses, bicycle, etc. Marine transportation with the help of boats, ships, cruises, etc., Air transportation with the help of helicopters, airplanes, etc. Rail transportation the help of train, and you are so many different types of transportation medium available in this whole world, a different type of transportation medium is available on the basis of traveling speed, traveling distance coverage capacity, running efficiency, running cost efficiency, luxury and preferences of different type of people and community. But the most preferable type of transportation medium is the one which is consisting of all the characteristics of a good way of transportation that is cost-efficient in terms of running, speed of running from one place to another in terms of transportation, the convenience of transportation in terms of easiness and luxury and the running mechanism functionality.

Traditionally, rails are the most preferred means of transportation because of their convenience and cost-effectiveness, and efficiency in terms of operation. But because of the long-term duration in terms of distance several different means of transportation was came into consideration by different industries and scientists. For one of the quickest means of transportation, air transportation is most preferred by all around the world. Air transportation with the help of helicopters and airplanes is also considered one of the most luxurious means of transportation and it is also one of the most modern and technologically advanced mediums of transportation. But, because of its costly nature not most of the people of the whole world prefer it as a primary or preferable means of transportation. Air transportation is mostly preferred by those people who used to travel from one country to another country or from one state to another

state which is located in distant areas. Whereas for a very short distance of transportation most of the people prefer to use their own personal vehicles such as motorbike, bicycle, four-wheeler, and others. In the metro cities of various countries including India, a lot of the people used to travel from one place to another with the help of their own private vehicle. But not everybody can afford their own personal vehicle so that most people used to travel by the help of public vehicles such as bus transportation, rail transportation, and metros. In metro cities, millions of people used to travel from one place to another with the help of various means of transportation for earning their livelihood on daily basis. Because of the continuous increase in the population of most of the countries including India.

Traditional means of transportation such as rail transportation somehow need some way of upgradations in terms of extensions and operational level. There is a great level of the increase taking place in the population of various metro cities, in which one of the top reasons is the high level of migration being taking place, especially in the search of employability and work. For employment and livelihood reasons, the travellers who used to travel daily from their homes to their job centres, mostly prefer the public transportation medium. The traditional means of transportation is somehow not so much quicker because of which the daily travellers must have to spend an average of four hours to five hours of traveling period on regular basis. Because of such a long duration of traveling on regular basis, most people get stressed, tired, and frustrated. Because of such reasons, the productivity of such people and the working abilities of such travellers get seriously affected. For making such condition improved and for enhancing the productivity level of the human resources, there is a need of some type of fast, advance and quick means of transportation. With the help of fast-medium of transportation, most of the traveling time which people spend in traveling long-distance journeys can be saved.

Virgin Hyperloop One is a system of sealed tube or system of tubes with very low atmospheric pressure throughout a pod, because of which the travel inside such tube is well freed from air resistance or any type of friction. The *Virgin Hyperloop One* can easily travel anything, including the passengers or any transportable material and objects from one place to another at a speed which is four times the speed of bullet train and two times the speed of airplanes, or a speed which is considered as hypersonic speeds in terms of fast transportation. *Virgin Hyperloop One* will also be considered as one of the most energy efficient means of transportation and very

much economical means of transportation in comparisons to the existing high-speed rail transportation systems.

India, one of the fastest-growing economies all around the whole world. Along with the economic growth and development, the growth is also taking places in terms of continuously increasing population too. For such growing population rising public transportation system is high on the agenda. The cities of any states and urban population plays a crucial and significant role in the overall growth of any country. As per the 2011 census, almost 31.2% of India's population (377 million) are resides in urban regions. According to the UN estimates, these numbers will easily reach up to 590 million by 2030 and will reach up to 875 million by 2050. Such enhancements will definitely require appropriate transportation facilities which must be fast, advance, quick and cost-effective in all terms.

I. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The transport system plays an integral role in its growth of any nation for a large number of reasons. It supports to the quick and cost-effective movement of raw materials, machinery, finished product, passengers from one place to the another in reliable manner. Transportation industries are significant role player for various types of industries in a very large manner. From Indians point of view, the role of the transport system is like a backbone for the economic development of India, as without a proper transportation system none of the produced goods can be transferrable from one place to the another. A decent transport system will broaden the marketplace for product, goods and services. It may also create the movement of raw materials, fuel, equipment, etc. to the places of production straightforward.

In the Pre-Independence, India's railways system was mostly Britishers-owned and were the railways corporations significantly operated by the British. However, post-Independence, it became a unified state enterprise. Indian Railways is India's biggest nationalized enterprise. Further, it's one in all the most important railway systems within the world, within the previous couple of years, the Indian Railways is taking initiatives in shifting to Public-Private Participation for constructing and operative and more productive means of railway infrastructure development. As fast means of transportation can easily support the structural transformation and can easily bring with three golden-opportunities for policy-makers; employment of migrants populations; growing urbanization and industrialization; and making and availing the higher education system and vocational education mechanisms for the ever increasing young Indian

population. Along with all such required level of functionalities, the requirements of an adequate level of transportation system are the need of the hour.

India's interstate migration has been rising over time, nearly doubling within the 2000s relative to the Nineties. And it's ever growing with a significant pace almost every year. The ultimate reason behind the same is earning livelihood and achieving the financial stabilities with the help of employment opportunities. The roles and challenge created by migration are going to be monumental in scope, because such migration activities encourage a very high level of transportation related activities, and will ultimately creating transportation industries to boom over the period of time.

India, is one of the most preferable place for the technology to seek out its roots. Because "India is a home to the quickest and ever-growing world economy power, because of a very large number of young generations, and the presence of one of the most sophisticated levels of engineering skills". And "India is one of the most preferable marketplace to launch new and advance transportation technology of *Virgin Hyperloop One* technology, due to all such above stated favourable conditions." Due to the significance of *Virgin Hyperloop One* technology, such project has additionally received approvals and supports from several governments, political parties and the corporates of India. Devendra Fadnavis, the Former Chief Minister of Maharashtra had voiced sturdy support for this project and had visited the project development sites, several times. The authorities signed a framework agreement with Hyperloop One at a world capitalist meet that was also attended by Honourable Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi.

II. METHODOLOGY

As per the requirements of the research study, the analysis is employed for the study of the descriptive sorting. For this reason, the accessible and required level of secondary data-based information was all at once and broadly used for the analysis purpose. A lot of distinguished level of analysis was employed in considering the accessible data and regarding in-depth investigation was associated with the topic in broader manner. For the Analysis & the Study of the Role and Importance of Futuristic & Fast Transportation Technology in Shaping the Bright Future of India, this research paper relies on the investigation which is connected and depending upon the information received and sourced from numerous libraries books, reliable records,

various journals, different types of magazines, pertinent books, topic-pertinent articles, reports, media, Etc.

III. ANALYSIS OF THE IMPORTANCE OF HYPERLOOP FUTURISTIC TRANSPORTATION TECHNOLOGY IN TERMS OF FASTEST TRANSPORTATION MEDIUM

Hyperloop consists of gas steel tubes that transport pods to transport the passengers from one point of place to any different place, all at a supersonic speed. In the year 2013, Elon Musk, who is one among the all-time best inventors and businessman of the twenty first century, place forth an advanced and emerging replacement technologically-based advanced which have a capability of travelling the masses at supersonic transportation speed, and such transport system referred as the *Virgin Hyperloop One* Fast Transportation Technology. *Virgin Hyperloop One* is so much quick that it can easily chop-down the overall travel times drastically by over three to fourth times in comparison to the traditional transportation and travelling mediums. And it will also additionally prove to be an better means of transportation as it will ultimately enhance the overall efficiency and cost-effectivity and a lot of environmentally friendly benefits are also there in comparisons to all other different transport systems presently used worldwide.

Virgin Hyperloop One is not only about the concerning speed, but it is additionally aimed to be bring a lot of environmentally friendly benefits in the long run. As one of the goals of *Virgin Hyperloop One* is to run the hyperloop entirely on the basis of renewable sources of energy. As per the results of a study conducted by *Virgin Hyperloop One* found that, if enforced, the Hyperloop may end up about fifty-eight percent of the overall emissions of the petroleum-based discharges, and will directly results in the reduction of all types of fuel-based pollution generating compounds in the environment. Additionally, *Virgin Hyperloop One* can prove to be a profitable deal in terms of cost-effectiveness and also for saving the overall operational cost on the basis of daily running procedures.

The development related cost in the context of costing of *Virgin Hyperloop One* is also very low in comparisons to the overall development costs of all the traditional mediums of transportations. And on the other hand, the overall maintenance cost of *Virgin Hyperloop One* is a way a lower than all the traditional mediums of transportations including traditional rail-based transportations. That can be a fruitful project for India in terms of managing national transport systems and for bring down the overall government expenditures on transportation and related

activities. The project can also prove to a fruitful plan in terms of reducing the cost related burden of Government of India.

The Hyperloop is comparatively efficient in comparisons to high-speed rail network referred to as the California High-Speed Rail, which has been approved at a staggering value of sixty billion United States Dollar, but the same length project can be completely developed in a mere six billion United States Dollar, which is almost one-tenth of the overall development cost of the high-speed rail network. Hyperloop is anticipated to value \$6 billion United States Dollar, as per the Elon Musk's white book citation. The globe will be going to welcome an advanced-level of replacement vision for the mass transportation system across the globe, which can be considered as the fifth mode of transportation.

IV. HIGHLIGHTING THE VIRGIN HYPERLOOP ONE FUTURISTIC TRANSPORTATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF INDIA

In India, *Virgin Hyperloop One* modern Transportation based Technology approaches towards operational-based approvals considerably through a Letter of Intent with the Indian Government for a projected route situated between Madras and Bengaluru regions. If all the functionality will go as per the planned and projected way, then the overall distance gap between these two areas of 345 kilometres will be easily travel in less than half an hour of time only, which was approximately three hours of journey previously. *Virgin Hyperloop One* modern Transportation Technology additionally signed various different agreements with the different state government of India, to make India's initial Hyperloop project connecting Amaravati to Vijayawada with an ultimate aim to complete the stated long-distance journey in just a 6-minute of complete travel. On Feb 2018, *Virgin Hyperloop One* has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the govt of Maharashtra to make a *Virgin Hyperloop One* project to initiate the installation project between Mumbai and Pune regions that will probably cut-down the overall journey time period from three hours of time to just simply about thirty minutes of travel time. Whereas, Indore-based Dinclix Groundworks' DGW Hyperloop signifies an Hyperloop passage way between Mumbai and Delhi, via Indore, Kota, and Jaipur, which will be going to change the whole story of transportation of future India.

The Smart City are the urban region that's extremely advanced in terms of overall infrastructure, properties, lands, communications technologies, and marketplaces viability. Smart Cities are the town, where advance technology is the principal infrastructure and also the basis for providing

essential goods and services to residents of such region. The key plan of advance and modern cities is that, the alliance of public services with diverse integrated conveyance system. Including Information Technology, modern means of transportations, better facilities in comparison to the other regions, modern industrial developments and several other facilities. therefore, *Virgin Hyperloop One* modern Transportation-Based technology can play a very significant and important role in each group of modern society, and such modern technologies will be a major role player in terms of making India's future much brighter in near future. Government of India's think-tank NITI Aayog has shaped a high-level panel to explore the technological and industrial viability of *Virgin Hyperloop One* technology for ultrahigh-speed travel system establishment in India.

The National Institution for Transforming India Aayog document, accessed by the Press Trust of India, says that visible and the possibilities of the rising and emerging transport technology systems in India are gaining the first-mover advantage on the world around. And It is very much essential to admire the advancement of technology into the technological and industrial viability of *Virgin Hyperloop One* technology. In a committee-based meeting of The Defence Research & Development Organisation's Chairman, the Delhi Metro Rail's decision maker, the Indian Institute of Technology Delhi's Director, and also the Chairman of Technology Information, India also discussed about the whole system development and related tasks of the *Virgin Hyperloop One* modern Transportation-based technology and assessment council as the members of it. All such will directly help and support the development of the *Virgin Hyperloop One* in India. India is keenly welcoming the modern and one of the fastest means of transportation technology, *Virgin Hyperloop One*, by taking all such important steps for bringing such high-level technology in the stipulated period of time.

V. NEW INCLINATIONS AND TECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN DEVELOPMENTS IN TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM

Technology plays a very significant role in making the country growing with more pace and encouraging advancements in terms of development of the whole public, to make them more technologically active, techno-advanced workable, and developed. It was proved several times that, technology have immense level of possibilities in terms of making the life of the people easy, enjoyable and productive in diverse ways. As we all know we are facing severe problematic situations which are created because of the increase in the levels of pollution, which

was ultimately because of increase in the consumption of public and private vehicles which utilizes petroleum-based fuel for running and operating. Increasing usages of private vehicles enhances twin severe problems, which are increase traffic and increased level of pollution which will directly results in global climate change.

Not everyone in the metro cities is capable of establish and set up their own houses in the areas where they are doing their jobs, employments and business-related works for their livelihoods. Due to which most of the people used to do daily up-downs from their home to the cities where they work, that can take nearly five hours of journey on daily basis. It is such a time-consuming task and will not generate any substantial and productive in results. That shows that transportation is solely the lifeline for these people, who resides at distant towns. In such case, the new, advanced and emerging transportation technology *Virgin Hyperloop One* will proved to be a reward.

With ever-changing demographics, and enlarged penetration of the internet and mobile, and the emergence of ideas like hybrid fuel, big data, machine-to-machine connectivity programmes, and embedded software package in automotive, the technological advancements take places with great pace and its continuously developing manifold over the period of time. It can be easily seeing by anyone that how technology is a playing a significant role in the number of the key areas wherever we can go. A huge level of investments was already made by many techno-giants in the field of information, data, and mobile application technologies to create their operations smarter and to make the world a more technologically-advanced place.

VI. ANALYSING THE PACE OF TECHNOLOGY ACCESSIBILITY IN TRANSPORTATION

The improved collaboration between automotive vehicle makers, fleet operators, technology, and wireless service suppliers to make new and innovative transport systems that will assist in achieving the upcoming and emerging targets. It might conjointly mean bigger use of technology that enhances communication and supply basis convenience. It is reportedly noted that the use of technology-based usage of mobile, smartphones, tablets, internet and geographical positioning system increase by multifold over the period of last five years because of the increase in the usages of various online cab booking software, such as, OLA, Uber and other online based application software. As when a transportation vehicle gets connected to the internet technology-based system, the connectivity ability can offer a position and open opportunities for the service

suppliers, that will ultimately enhanced the transportation mechanism, this will booming the use of riding-based app technology which results in the increase in the amount of technology-driven road transportation by an enormous 75%, but it will also increase the consumption of petroleum based products , that will somehow increases the pollution in the environment. Technology has both sides, mostly it is a good thing which encourages the overall ease of functionality, but on the other side it also makes some areas complex. GPS and cloud-based connected vehicles, and victimization ITS (intelligent transport systems), are all creating their presence in Indian cities, giving passengers the convenience of travelling time by helping in assessing the location-based data, which will help the people to update their works, useability, schedules, routes, etc. on the basis of their conveniences, just by clicking on their smartphones.

The investments made by big techno-giants within the said areas, provides an emerging framework for booming their functionality along with their integration with several other larger corporates. That's also requires a bigger degree of communication between the system and important service providers, with the use of Internet of Things (IoT) at the core, where almost all of the activities of top-level corporates as well as the others get benefitted at large. The maximum benefit is driven with the adoption of modern technology, as it's imperative to make surroundings that fosters bigger public-private partnership models to roll out solutions quicker, facilitates nearer collaboration between completely different stakeholders and aims at achieving inclusivity.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

India government is focusing towards implementation of more futuristic and advance technological-based upgradations in their transportation systems through the utilization of modern transportation system as implementation of such modern technology will not only an opportunity generation for the country's bright future, but also beneficial from environment point of view. The modern implementation comes as no surprise for a country like India, because once such step will be taken for the betterment of Indian transportation, the whole transportation system get benefitted in the near future, some of the key areas like Indian atmosphere conditions will get better, environment pollution related conditions can be minimized, economy stability can be access through more quicker transportation system, safety of the whole transportation can be enhanced which will directly decreases the accident numbers, etc. The recent reports of the World Health Organization signify that seven of the world's top most polluted cities in terms of

worse air quality index are situated in India with the worst levels of Particulate Matter 10. All such because of the continuous increase in the utilization of petroleum-based fuel in various types of automobiles. Increase in the level of pollution and because of the worse air quality index of the country gives birth to several types of problematic situations in terms of health, businesses and others. And on the other hand, with the continuous increase in the level of private as well public vehicles, the overall transportation system of India is getting converted into complex on day-by-day basis.

As because of massive and continuously increase in number of automobiles the increase in the number of daily accidents and other incidents also get enhanced, accordingly. Due to which the overall road accident-based deaths cases in India showed a massive rise of nine per cent over the past four years, that was actually massive. And according to the one of the IIT Madras study found that, metropolis roads and transportation system costs around \$10 billion or almost Rs. 60,000 crores annually as a result of fuel wastes due to the utilization of private and public vehicles, which will also ultimately be enhancing the level of pollution in the environment. Such a huge amount was wasted almost every year by our transportation mechanisms and system, which if utilized for any of some other reasons, it will be fruitful for the whole country at a large level. This huge increase in vehicle traffic in cities is one of the major contributors to the increase pollution of air and worsening air quality index.

At present, India is doing intensive work in the areas of electrical and hybrid cars, element fuel cells, multiple battery technologies, and additionally finding new ways in which the generation of Compressed Natural Gas can take place at an effective and efficient manner, to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and for also enhance the cost-effectiveness. Compressed Natural Gas, as an alternate supply of fuel for transportation, had already gained mass acceptance in the past few years but somehow it was not proved to the best source of energy fuel in making the Indian transportation system, cost-effective and pollution free. Some of the additional innovation and technology-based upgradation is actually the need of the hour, which will provide a better opportunity for encouraging engineering-based solutions and diverse experimentations within the field of alternate powertrains and transportation medium.

The success of the experiment of Hyperloop is a propounding welcome for its functioning in India in the upcoming years. For such reason, the company gets into a contract with Bangalore airport as well as the Punjab transportation department. Hyperloop could also be a brand-new

reasonably ground for the transportation system presently in development by a range of companies, it will make it possible for the passengers to move at a speed over 1200 kilometers each hour in an exceedingly floating pod. As we all know that in most of the Indian metropolitan cities, the employees and labor have to do daily up-downs for earning their livelihood. And for that reason, most of the time of such people was wasted in transportation. Such people spend almost four hours of time in transportation for the reason of moving towards their respective working centers.

Most of the times, these people will be spent by staying away from their family members, sometimes that can be a major reason for hampering their family relationship and can ultimately create dissatisfaction, stress, mental pressure, fights and other crucial incidents, just because of the distances created because of the long-distance transportation. For all such people *Virgin Hyperloop One* would possibly prove to be a helping hand and new supporting mechanisms, which will not only make their life easy but also make them stress-free in almost every sense. It will be accustomed in taking the pressure off over the gridlocked roads, and help in making travel system between cities and states easier, and probably unlocking major economic benefits for the country, as a result.

We can easily analyses the captive abilities of this new transportation system with the fact that it can complete the 3 hours of journey in just 35 minutes of time. *Virgin Hyperloop One* is capable of transporting more than 200 million passengers every year when it will start functioning. Such innovative and technology-driven advanced transportation system will bring various type of opportunities for the country India in the upcoming future, as such project will bring a very large amount of infrastructure-based investment that will directly or indirectly generate the employment opportunities for over 1.8 million people and it will also generate a huge amount of economic profit for country India. *Virgin Hyperloop One* will be cheaper and faster than the train or other automobile travel, and it can be a major shifter for making the whole environment pollution free, at least the level of pollution which was created every year by the public and private transportation system. The company in addition claims that such new technology will conjointly become more quicker and cheaper in comparison to our traditional high-speed train. In near future, *Virgin Hyperloop One* will prove to be one of the most innovative, advanced, efficient, eco-friendly, and easy to operate means of transportation system, which have both the benefits of cost efficiency and profitability.

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